

Kinetic Salt Effect in Methyl Alcohol Solutions.
The Reaction between Sodium Bromacetate and Sodium
Methoxide.

BY A. N. KAPPANNA AND H. W. PATWARDHAN.

Brönsted's theory of the kinetics of ionic reactions provides a method (Kappanna, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 45, 419) for testing the Debye-Hückel expression for the activity coefficients of ions in dilute solutions, which is particularly useful in cases, where the activity coefficients cannot be determined otherwise. Investigations in this field have so far been confined to studies of aqueous solutions or of solutions in mixtures of alcohol and water. The present investigation relates to a pure nonaqueous solvent.

The reaction between sodium bromacetate and sodium methoxide in methyl alcohol was found by Senter and Wood (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 1070) to be bimolecular and to proceed as follows:—

The velocity was however found to increase with increasing total initial concentration. This is to be expected, as the reaction takes place between similarly charged ions. The reaction is well suited for our purpose, since throughout the reaction the ionic strength remains constant and no side-reactions occur.

The kinetics of this reaction have been studied over a wide range of ionic strengths in moderately dilute and concentrated solutions but unfortunately the work had to be discontinued. The study of more dilute solutions will be resumed as soon as circumstances permit.

EXPERIMENTAL.

C. P. methyl alcohol (free from acetone) obtained from the Mysore Iron works, Bhadravati was used. It was practically free from acetone; only very slight traces could be detected.

To remove the traces of water, the alcohol was allowed to stand over fresh lime (well mixed) for about 24 hours and refluxed for six hours before distillation. The constant boiling middle fraction was collected and subjected to the same treatment as before. The product of this second distillation was then treated with sodium and distilled, using a long twelve bulb fractionating column. The constant boiling middle fraction was collected and stored in a big glass reservoir, darkened from outside to protect the alcohol from the action of light and fitted with a tube communicating with a phosphorus pentoxide bulb. A siphon tube enabled the alcohol to be taken out when required. Thus sodium methoxide solutions in methyl alcohol were always freshly prepared, standardised and diluted to the required extent just before use. Kahlbaum's pure monobromacetic acid, purified by recrystallisation and dried in a desiccator over phosphorus pentoxide, was dissolved in methyl alcohol when necessary in required quantities, standardised and diluted to the desired extent before use. Sodium bromacetate was formed in the reaction mixture itself by the addition of a calculated amount of sodium methoxide solution. Merck's extra pure sodium bromide, purified by recrystallisation and dried, was used.

The following procedure was adopted for studying the reaction. Adequate quantities of the reaction mixture were pipetted out at different intervals of time and mixed with known volumes of hydrochloric acid of known concentration, the quantity of the acid added being always in excess of the amount necessary for the neutralisation of the unreacted sodium methoxide. The excess of acid was titrated against, either $\cdot 1 N$ - or $\cdot 05 N$ - sodium hydroxide and the quantity of sodium methoxide in the reaction mixture at the time of pipetting out computed by difference. Velocity measurements were carried out at $50^{\circ} \pm 0\cdot 05^{\circ}$ and $60^{\circ} \pm 0\cdot 05^{\circ}$ in an electrically heated and regulated thermostat.

Tables I-IV give some results of velocity measurements at 60° and are typical. Under 1 and 2 are given the equivalents of unreacted bromacetate and sodium methoxide respectively at the different time intervals in terms of c. c. of $\cdot 05 N$ solutions.

TABLE I.

Vol. titrated = 10 c.c.

Sodium methylate = 0.047 N; Sodium bromacetate = 0.1 N.

Time (min.).	1.	2.	0.434·k.
0	7.80	18.47	—
30	5.90	16.57	0.04629
60	4.75	15.42	0.04596
90	3.80	14.47	0.05136
150	2.60	13.27	0.04667
210	1.80	12.47	0.04519
270	1.00	11.67	0.04806
			Mean 0.04725

TABLE II.

Vol. titrated = 10 c.c.

Sodium methylate = 0.064 N; Sodium bromacetate = 0.0333 N.

Time (min.).	1.	2.	0.434·k.
0	12.30	6.08	—
60	10.90	4.68	0.03279
120	9.90	3.68	0.03318
180	9.15	2.93	0.03367
240	8.60	2.38	0.03373
360	7.80	1.58	0.03459
420	7.50	1.28	0.03533
			Mean 0.03388

TABLE III.

Volume titrated = 25 c.c.

Sodium methylate = 0.018 N; Sodium bromacetate = 0.04 N.

Time (min.).	1.	2.	0.494 <i>k</i> .
0	8.70	19.37	—
60	7.55	18.22	0.02733
120	6.65	17.82	0.02718
180	5.80	16.47	0.02747
240	5.10	15.77	0.02784
60	4.00	14.67	0.02820
480	3.20	13.87	0.02825
			Mean 0.02771

TABLE IV.

Vol. titrated = 25 c.c.

Sodium methylate = 0.027 N; Sodium bromacetate = 0.012 N.

Time (min.).	1.	2.	0.434 <i>k</i> .
0	13.40	5.85	—
60	12.95	5.40	0.02207
180	12.15	4.60	0.02277
270	11.65	4.10	0.02298
360	11.25	3.70	0.02263
480	10.70	3.15	0.02362
			Mean 0.02281

Table V gives the results of all the experiments at 50° and 60°.

TABLE V.

Conc. of sod. bromacetate (N).	Conc. of sod. methylate (N).	Total ionic strength (μ).	$0.434 k_{30}^{\circ}$.	$0.434 k_{60}^{\circ}$.	$\frac{k_{60}^{\circ}}{k_{30}^{\circ}}$.
0.2000	0.2888	0.48880	0.09900	0.03030	3.268
0.2000	0.09328	0.29328	0.07200	0.02200	3.273
0.1000	0.04664	0.14664	0.04725	0.01420	3.327
0.0333	0.06443	0.09773	0.03388	0.01035	3.273
0.0400	0.01866	0.05866	0.02271	0.00855	3.241
0.0120	0.02710	0.03910	0.02281	0.00700	3.260
0.0060	0.01355	0.01955	0.01801	0.005894	3.271
Mean					3.273

Figures in Table V indicate clearly that the velocity of the reaction continues to increase with increasing total ionic concentration. If A and B denote respectively the bromacetate and methylate ions and k , the bimolecular velocity constant, then according to Brönsted's theory,

$$k = \text{Constant} \cdot \frac{f_A \cdot f_B}{f_{AB}}, \quad \dots (1)$$

where f_A , f_B and f_{AB} stand for the activity coefficients of the bromacetate, methylate and the collision complex ions respectively. A and B being of the same sign, AB will be a bivalent ion. Equation (1) can be put as

$$\log k = \log (\text{constant}) + \log \frac{f_A \cdot f_B}{f_{AB}}. \quad \dots (2)$$

According to Debye, $-\log f_{ion} = a \cdot z^2 \cdot \sqrt{\mu}$,

where a is a constant at a definite temperature and solvent, and z , the valence of the ion. Therefore

$$-\log \frac{f_A \cdot f_B}{f_{AB}} = -2 \cdot a \cdot z_A \cdot z_B \cdot \sqrt{\mu}.$$

Since $z_A = z_B = 1$, we could write $\log k = 2 \cdot a \cdot \sqrt{\mu}$... (3)

This equation is applicable only to very dilute solutions. In so far as it is applicable, we should get a straight line on plotting $\log k$

against $\sqrt{\mu}$, the value of the slope being equal to $2a$. On plotting $\log (0.434 k.a. 10^3)$ against $\sqrt{\mu}$ (abscissae), it was found that the curve obtained was concave downwards and not a straight line. This is to be expected, as we are dealing with fairly high concentrations.

At 25° , a is equal to 2.112 for methyl alcohol and this value increases slightly with temperature, since the product of the dielectric constant and the temperature gradually diminishes with increase in temperature and a varies inversely as $(DT)^{\frac{3}{2}}$. On this basis, the slope of the curve referred to above, should have a value at least equal to about 4.30 in the ideal region and at higher concentrations this value should be expected to gradually diminish. The average value for $\frac{d \log k}{d \sqrt{\mu}}$ between 0.01955μ and 0.05866μ in our experiments is about 1.70, which is even less than half the value predicted by Debye-Hückel theory for the ideal region. Experimental evidence shows that strictly speaking

$$-\log f_{ion} = a.z^2 \sqrt{\mu} + \beta.c, \quad \dots (4)$$

β has a small value in the region of concentrations used in this investigation. But it is difficult to expect that the slope of the curve between 0.0μ and 0.02μ to be more than double of what it is immediately above 0.020μ . It would appear therefore that the Debye-Hückel theory does not satisfactorily explain the course of this reaction with variation in total ionic strength.

Temperature coefficient of the reaction rate.—It will be observed from the last column of Table V, that $\frac{k_{60}^\circ}{k_{50}^\circ}$ remains pretty steady throughout the range of ionic strengths examined. This is in accordance with the observation made by one of us in a previous communication (*loc.cit.*) as demanded by the Debye-Hückel expression or the Ghosh expression for the activity coefficients of ions.

It will also be noticed that the value 3.273 for the temperature coefficient of the bimolecular velocity constant in methyl alcohol is very high as compared with the usual value, 2–2.5, for the same in aqueous solutions.

Neutral salt effect.—Sodium bromide was chosen as the neutral salt, as its solubility in methyl alcohol happens to be fairly high. Table VI gives the results carried out in a definite reaction mixture.

TABLE VI.

Conc. of sodium methoxide = 0.0187M; Conc. of sodium bromacetate = 0.04N. Temp. = 60°.

Conc. of NaBr (N).	μ .	$0.434 k \times 10^3$.
0	0.0587	28.00
0.040	0.0987	32.29
0.100	0.1587	41.75
0.200	0.2587	59.23
0.400	0.4587	86.93
0.600	0.6587	112.28
0.800	0.8587	142.50

Here also the velocity gradually increases with increasing total ionic concentration. But a comparison of these figures with velocities at corresponding total ionic strengths (while total μ is made up only by the concentrations of the reacting components) shows that when sodium bromide makes up the total ionic strength, the velocities are somewhat lower. This is no doubt due to specific ionic influences, since we are dealing with moderately concentrated solutions.

Summary.

A study of the kinetics of the reaction between sodium monobromacetate and sodium methoxide in methyl alcohol has been made at 50° and 60°, at various ionic strengths over the range 0.01955 μ —0.4890 μ .

In accordance with Brönsted's theory, the reaction rate increases with increase in ionic strength.

For the ideal dilute region, Debye-Hückel theory predicts that $\frac{d \log k}{d \sqrt{\mu}}$ should be equal to at least 4.3. The average experimental value for the same in the region between 0.0195 μ and 0.05866 μ has been found to be 1.70, which is even less than half the value predicted by theory for more dilute solutions. It is therefore inferred that even in more dilute solutions, the agreement between the experimental values and values predicted by theory may not be even approximate,

The temperature coefficient $\frac{k_{60^\circ}}{k_{50^\circ}}$ of the bimolecular velocity constant remains steady over the entire range of ionic strengths examined. The value 3.273 for the temperature coefficient of this bimolecular velocity constant in methyl alcohol is very high as compared with the usual value, 2–2.5 for bimolecular reactions in aqueous solutions.

The effect of adding sodium bromide in different quantities to the reaction mixture is examined over the wide range of concentrations. The velocity of reaction increases with increasing ionic strength but not so rapidly as when ionic strength is increased by the variation in the concentrations of the reactants.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
COLLEGE OF SCIENCE,
NAGPUR, C. P.

Received August 31, 1931.